

Complexes of some Transition Elements with 2-(2'-pyridyl)Benzimidazole

S. P. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARJEE and L. K. MISHRA

[Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800005].

Complex compounds of Co(II & III), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II), Rh(III), Ir(III) and Pt(II) with 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole are reported. Structure and bonding of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of magnetic susceptibility, electrical conductance data, electronic reflectance and absorption spectra and infrared spectra measurements. The different crystal field parameters of Ni(II) complexes have also been calculated.

THE molecule 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole (A) is of interest because of its structural similarity to 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline in containing the grouping (-N=C-C=N-) and also having the biologically important imidazole grouping. It gives colour reactions with Cu(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Fe(II) and Fe(III)^{1,2}. The ligand has also been recommended as a suitable reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of iron(II)².

From IR spectra of the metal complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazole and 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole, it has been found³⁻⁵ that the ligands generally behave as bidentates and coordination takes place through the pyridine nitrogen and the tertiary nitrogen atom of the imidazole ring as shown in B. In the present paper we report the complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole (PBH) with Ni(II), Co(II & III), Cu(II), Rh(III), Ir(III), Pd(II) and Pt(II). The isola-

tion, structure, bonding and geometry of these metal complexes are discussed.

Results and Discussion :

Like 2, 2'-bipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline, 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (PBH) is also a strong ligand and has been found to form various stable complexes with transition metal ions. With Ni(II) and Co(II & III), it forms complexes containing two and three ligand molecules. The tris chelated Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes, $[M(PBH)_3]X_2$ (where $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , ClO_4^- and $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$), are obtained by refluxing and concentrating a stoichiometric mixture of an ethanolic or aqueous ethanolic solution of respective metal salts and the ligand. The complexes are insoluble in water but dissolve in ethanol and DMF. The electrolytic conductance values ($146-170 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$; Table—A) of these complexes in DMF solution are in the range expected for bivalent electrolytes.⁶ At room temperature, Ni(II) complexes exhibit magnetic moment values (Table—A) in the range 3.01—3.18 B.M. as expected for octahedral nickel(II) ion in weak field.⁷ The magnetic moment value (Table—A) of tris chelated Co(II) complexes are straight forward and are in the range of 5.12—5.23 B.M., usually expected for high spin octahedral Co(II) complexes.

The tris chelated cobalt(III) complex, $[Co(PBH)_3]Cl_3$ is obtained by ligand replacement reaction from $[Co(NH_3)_6]Cl_3$ in hot aqueous ethanol. The different complex salts, $[Co(PBH)_3]X_3$ (where $X=Br^-$, I^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^-), are prepared by metathetic

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TABLE A—COLOUR, MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES (304-305°K), MOLAR CONDUCTANCE VALUES (in DMF at 28°C) AND SOLID REFLECTANCE BAND POSITION OF COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES OF 2-(2-Pyridyl) BENZIMIDAZOLE (L).

Compound	Colour	λ_m ohm ⁻¹ cm ²	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Spectral band position (cm ⁻¹)	
[CoL ₂ Cl ₂]	Rose-red	45	4.96	19,230	22,700 sh
[CoL ₂ Br ₂]	Rose-red	46	4.91	18,516	21,800 sh
[CoL ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Buff-colour	38	5.00	20,308	21,740 sh
[CoL ₂ I ₂]	Buff-colour	40	5.02	18,180 sh	22,200 sh
[CoL ₃]Cl ₂	Cream-colour	158	5.13	18,180 sh	22,000 sh
[CoL ₃]Br ₂	Cream-colour	158	5.18	18,180 sh	22,200 sh
[CoL ₃]I ₂	Cream-colour	147	5.23	—	—
[CoL ₃](ClO ₄) ₂	Cream-colour	151	5.16	18,180 sh	22,140 sh
Co(PB) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Orange-yellow	3	2.65	—	—
[NiL ₂ Cl ₂]	Bluish-green	38	3.31	10,180	16,210
[NiL ₂ Br ₂]	Bluish-green	42	3.39	10,100	16,621
[NiL ₂ I ₂]	Yellowish-green	—	3.36	—	—
[NiL ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Violet-blue	42	3.35	10,416	16,905 13,160
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	Bluish-green	132	3.33	10,410	16,830
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Br ₂ ·H ₂ O	Bluish-green	128	3.28	—	—
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Bluish-green	141	3.29	—	—
[Ni(PB) ₂]4H ₂ O	Cream-colour	5	3.06	10,860 (ϵ_{max}^{-8})	17,670 (ϵ_{max}^{-12})
[NiL ₃]Cl ₂	Rose-red	—	3.12	10,870	17,850
[NiL ₃]Br ₂	Rose-red	—	3.13	10,660 (ϵ_{max}^{-9})	17,835 (ϵ_{max}^{-21})
[NiL ₃](ClO ₄) ₂	Rose-red	146	3.19	10,870	17,850
[NiL ₃](NO ₃) ₂	Rose-red	158	3.16	10,880 (ϵ_{max}^{-10})	17,670 (ϵ_{max}^{-24})
[PdL ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Cream-yellow	142	Dia.	27,000	
[PdL ₂]SO ₄	Cream-yellow	140	—	27,000	

(ε_{max} in DMF)

reaction from the complex chloride. The complexes are soluble in water and ethanol as well. In aqueous solutions, the complexes show molar conductance value (350—374 ohm⁻¹), normally found for 1:3 electrolyte.

The diacido bis chelated Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes $[M(PBH)_2X_2]$, ($X=Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- and NCS^-) are obtained by refluxing 1:2 molar proportion of appropriate metal salts and ligand in dry ethanol. Nickel(II) complexes $[Ni(PBH)_2X_2]$ are insoluble in water and ethanol but dissolve in DMF. In DMF solution they show some conductance value which may be attributed to solvation. Appreciable conductance values of $[Ni(dipy)_2X_2]$ and $[Ni(pyAH)_2X_2]$ ($pyAH=pyridylhydrazones$) in nitromethane or methanol has been attributed to such solvation.^{8,9}

The complexes are paramagnetic and at room temperature the magnetic moment value (3.31—3.39 B.M.) of the complexes, suggest high spin octahedral environment of nickel(II) ion in weak octahedral field or tetragonal field. The i.r. spectrum of dithiocyanato complex does not exhibit any splitting of CN band. It only exhibits a very strong and broad CN stretch at 2080 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(CS)$ could not be identified definitely due to ligand vibrations. In the lower region the complex exhibits $\delta(NCS)$ at 500 cm⁻¹. Thus from the position of $\nu(CN)$ and $\delta(NCS)$ bands, N-Coordination of thiocyanate group is suggested.¹⁰

Rose-red or buff coloured bis chelated Co(II) complexes $[Co(PBH)_2X_2]$ are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but dissolve, on warming, in DMF giving orange brown colouration. Such solutions show appreciable conductance (38-65 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) which may probably be due to solvation or decomposition. The i.r. spectra of the complex $[Co(PBH)_2(NCS)_2]$ shows a strong and broad band at 2095 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder near 2010 cm⁻¹ (CN stretch). CS stretching band of thiocyanato group could not be identified. However, keeping in mind the class 'a' character of cobalt(II) and the bulky size of the ligand molecule N-coordination of isothiocyanate group is suggested. These diacido complexes, $[Co(PBH)_2X_2]$ are paramagnetic and their moment values (4.90—5.02 B.M.) at room temperature suggest them to have octahedral structure.

Besides diacido complexes of Ni(II), diaquo bis chelated complex salts of the type $[Ni(PBH)_2(H_2O)_2]X_2 \cdot nH_2O$, (where $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , or NO_3^- and $n=1$ or 2) are obtained as light green precipitates when

hydrated nickel(II) salts are refluxed with ethanolic solution of the ligand (1:2 molar ratio). The complexes are soluble in DMF or boiling water. In DMF solution the conductance values are slightly lower than expected for bi-univalent electrolyte (Table—A). At room temperature, they show magnetic moments in the range of 3.28—3.32 B.M. The i.r. spectrum of the complex nitrate $[Ni(PBH)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ shows the characteristic frequencies of uncoordinated nitrate group (NO stretch at 1381 and $\delta(NO_3)$ at 828 cm⁻¹). The spectrum exhibits a medium and very broad band near 3450 cm⁻¹ and a medium and broad band at 850 cm⁻¹. The broad band at 3450 cm⁻¹ is indicative of lattice water and the band at 850 cm⁻¹ is probably due to coordinated water molecules.¹¹ The complexes, on heating gradually lose uncoordinated water molecules below 120°C. The remaining two water molecules are lost at about 200-220°C which supports their coordination. The colour, magnetic moment values and reflectance spectra of the dehydrated products are similar to those found for $[Ni(PBH)_2X_2]$ ($X=Cl^-$ or Br^-).

In alkaline solution the NH group of bis chelated complex $[M(PBH)_2X_2]$ is deprotonated and forms inner complexes $M(PB)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ ($M=Co(II)$ or $Ni(II)$). These are insoluble in water but dissolve in benzene, acetone, D.M.F. etc. As expected the DMF solution is nonconducting. On heating the complexes gradually lose water molecules and become anhydrous at about 150—160°C, indicating that some water molecules are either coordinated or strongly bonded in crystal lattice. At room temperature $Ni(PB)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ show magnetic moment value of 3.01 B.M. indicative of octahedral environment of nickel (II) in weak field.

The magnetic moment value of $Co(PB)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ is anomalously low and is found to be 2.65 B.M. at 305°K. The magnetic moment of six coordinated cobalt(II) complexes are in the range of either 1.9—2.2 B.M. for low spin or 4.8—5.2 B.M. for high spin complexes. The magnetic moment of tetrahedral complexes are temperature independent and are in the range 4.2 to 4.7 B.M. The complexes with intermediate magnetic moments are viewed as anomalous and are due to an equilibrium mixture of complexes in two spin states, in which each of the electronic levels provide different amount of spin and orbital angular momentum to the magnetic moment values.¹² In present case, the low magnetic moment value of $Co(PB)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, may be due to the same cause of spin state equilibrium with some orbital

contribution from the supper exchange coupling of mobile π -system of the ligand.

The oxidation of an aqueous ethanolic solution of bis chelated cobalt(II) complex with alkaline H_2O_2 (pH 10–12) resulted in the formation of bis chelated cobalt(III) complex $Co(PB)_2(H_2O)OH$. The complex base is soluble in dil. acids and form soluble complex salts $[Co(PB)_2(H_2O)_2]X_n \cdot nH_2O$ ($X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-, ClO_4^-$ and $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$ and $n=2$ or 3). The complex salts are diamagnetic and dissolves in water. The aqueous solution of the complex salts show electrical conductance value (Table—A) of 1:1 electrolyte.

Copper(II) forms complexes containing one and two ligand molecules. The complexes containing two ligand molecules $Cu(PBH)_2X_2 \cdot nH_2O$ ($X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-, \frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}, ClO_4^-$ and CH_3COO^- and $n=0$ or 1) are obtained by simple mixing or mixing and refluxing an ethanolic or aqueous ethanolic solution of appropriate copper(II) salts with stoichiometric proportion of ligand. The complexes are insoluble in water but slightly soluble in DMF and ethanol. These are paramagnetic and their magnetic moment values are in the range 1.80–1.88 B.M. (Table—B). The complexes containing one ligand molecule $[Cu$

TABLE B—COLOUR, MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUE AT 305°K AND SOLID REFLECTANCE BAND OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES WITH 2—(2'-PYRIDYL) BENZIMIDAZOLE (L).

Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Spectral bands.
CuL_2Cl_2	Green	1.82	14,286—12,800
CuL_2Br_2	Deep green	1.80	13,501—11,765
$CuL_2(NO_3)_2$	Bluish-green	1.86	14,500—12,800
$CuL_2(CH_3COO)_2$	Bluish-green	1.88	16,660—14,280
$CuL_2SO_4 \cdot H_2O$	Bluish-green	1.82	14,120—12,800
$CuLCl_2$	Yellowish-green	1.78	13,585—12,750
$CuLBr_2$	Brown	1.72	13,500—12,000
$CuL(NCS)_2$	Yellowish-green	1.83	14,120—13,000

$(PBH)X_2]$ (where $X = Cl^-$ or Br^-) are obtained when methanolic solution of copper(II) halides and ligand solution in acetone is mixed and refluxed for a few minutes. The diisothiocyanato complex $Cu(PBH)(NCS)_2$ is obtained as deep green precipitate when aqueous ethanolic solution of dichloro complex

$Cu(PBH)Cl_2$ is refluxed with excess of KCNS on steam bath. The magnetic moment values of diacido complexes are in the range 1.73–1.83 B.M. The IR spectrum of $[Cu(PBH)(NCS)_2]$ exhibits a strong broad band at 2100 and a weak band at 2055 cm^{-1} (CN stretching frequencies). The (CS) stretching band could not be identified but σ (NCS) is observed at 490 cm^{-1} . Thus from broadness of CN stretching band and observed position of σ (NCS) band, N-coordination of thiocyanate group is suggested.

With Rh(III) and Ir(III) the resulting diamagnetic complexes can be represented as $[M(PBH)_2X_2]^+$ and $[M(PBH)_2CINCS]^+$ (where $M = Rh, Ir$; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-, NO_2^-$ or N_3^-).

$[Rh(PBH)_2Cl_2]Cl \cdot 2H_2O$ and $[Ir(PBH)_2Cl_2]Cl \cdot 2H_2O$ have been conveniently prepared by warming aqueous solutions of $RhCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ (1M) and $(NH_4)_3IrCl_6$ (1M) respectively with 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole (2M) dissolved in minimum volume of dil. HCl as to have a pH of ca 3.0. Both the species are slightly soluble in water, the solubility however, increases on warming.

The other diacido species have been prepared by the general reaction :

and

The diiodo species are the least soluble. Complexes of the rhodium series are relatively more soluble than the iridium series.

$[Rh(PBH)_2Cl_2]^+$ and $[Ir(PBH)_2Cl_2]^+$ are very resistant to either acid or base hydrolysis. Their molar conductivity in aqueous solution show these to be typically 1:1 electrolytes : $[Rh(PBH)_2Cl_2]Cl \cdot 2H_2O$: 112 ohm^{-1} and $[Ir(PBH)_2Cl_2]Cl \cdot 2H_2O$: 98 ohm^{-1} .

The thermal stability of the two complexes are also similar. Decomposition starts at about 270°C and is completed at 570°C .

The X-ray powder photographs of the two samples are also identical. The compounds, therefore, appear to be isomorphous.

The IR spectra show slight increase in the frequency of the pyridine breathing vibration (996 cm^{-1}) to 1008 cm^{-1} and 1005 cm^{-1} in case of Rh and Ir complexes respectively. This increase can be attributed to coordination from the pyridine nitrogen to the metal ion. The N-H stretching frequency shifts to 3210 and 3195 cm^{-1} in the above cases from 3247 cm^{-1} in the case of ligand.

Martin *et al.*¹⁴ on the basis of the splitting of the in plane out of plane C-H vibrations of the bipyridyl, assigned the cis configuration to $[\text{Rh}(\text{bipy})_2\text{X}_2] \cdot \text{X} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. No such splitting has been observed in the case of $[\text{Rh}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ or $(\text{Ir}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2)\text{X}$. When, however, the IR spectra of $[\text{Rh}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$, NO_2 and $[\text{Ir}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_2$ on KBr disc are compared with that of the cis $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$, then from the ν_1 and ν_2 frequencies it can be suggested, according to Gatehouse,¹⁵ that the Rh and Ir complexes might have trans configuration :

Complex	$\nu_3(\text{asym})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_1(\text{sym})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_2(\text{bending})$ cm^{-1}
$\text{Cis}[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	1409 vs	1316 s, 1340	819 s, 829s
$[\text{Rh}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_2$	1400 s	1312 s	829 s
$[\text{Ir}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_2$	1386 s	1332 s	820 m
$\text{Cis}[\text{Pt}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	1415 s	1330 s 1310 s	826 s

The far infrared spectra of $[\text{Rh}(\text{PBH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ir}(\text{PBH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ show one strong band at 336 cm^{-1} and 304 cm^{-1} respectively. These are assigned to $\nu(\text{M-Cl})$ with trans arrangement of chlorine, taking into consideration the splitting of this band in the cis arrangement in cases of $[\text{Rh}(\text{bipy})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Rh}(o\text{-phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Ir}(\text{bipy})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{Ir}(o\text{-phen})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ as shown by Gillard and Heaton.¹⁶

The IR frequencies of the chloro-isothiocyanato complexes : $\nu(\text{CN})$ 2108, 2081 and $\nu(\text{CS})$ 755 for $[\text{Rh}(\text{PBH})_2\text{CINCS}]\text{SCN}$, and $\nu(\text{CN})$ 2108, 2060 and $\nu(\text{CS})$ 758 for $[\text{Ir}(\text{PBH})_2\text{CINCS}]\text{SCN}$ are in consistent with N bonded NCS. The diazido complexes, as expected, show ν_3 frequencies at 2103 and 2104 cm^{-1} for Rh(III) and Ir(III) complexes respectively.

Palladium(II) and platinum(II) form planar diamagnetic diacido complexes, $[\text{M}(\text{PBH})\text{X}_2]$, ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$,

Br^- , I^- , NCS^- and NO_2^-). The dichloro complexes are easily obtained by treating an acid solution (pH : 3-6) of palladium(II) or platinum(II) chloride with an ethanolic solution of the ligand. The other diacido complexes are obtained by refluxing an aqueous suspension of dichloro complexes with excess of sodium or potassium salt of respective acido ions. These are also prepared by treating aqueous salt of metal chloride containing excess of NaX ($\text{X}=\text{Br}^-$, I^- , NO_2^- or NCS^-) with an ethanolic solution of the ligand. In case of $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})(\text{NCS})_2]$, at first a rose red crystal of $(\text{PBH}_2^+)_2[\text{Pd}(\text{SCN})_4]$ is precipitated which on refluxing changes into the orange-yellow diisothiocyanato complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})(\text{NCS})_2]$. Unlike the other diacido complexes, the dinitrato and sulphato complexes of palladium(II) could not be isolated from aqueous or acidic solution of $\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and PdSO_4 respectively, but instead the bis chelated complex salts, $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})_2]\text{SO}_4$ were formed. The complexes are insoluble in water but slightly soluble in DMF. The DMF solution of complex nitrate, shows molar conductance value of $\sim 142\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2$ at 28°C .

The IR spectra of $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})(\text{NCS})_2]$ and $(\text{Pt}(\text{PBH})(\text{NCS})_2)$ exhibit CN stretch at 2105 and 2125 cm^{-1} , and CS stretch at 850 and 855 cm^{-1} respectively. $\delta(\text{NCS})$ of these complexes are observed at 475 and 495 cm^{-1} which suggests the coordination of NCS through nitrogen atom. The coordination of thiocyanate group with soft acid Pd(II) and Pt(II) through nitrogen in preference to soft sulphur is probably due to greater steric volume and π -bonding character of the ligand molecule. The dinitro complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{PBH})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{PBH})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ exhibits the i.r. vibrations of cis coordinated nitro group with Pd(II) and Pt(II).

Spectral Behaviour :

The electronic absorption spectra (in DMF) of the tris chelated complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{PBH})_3]\text{X}_2$, show a very strong charge transfer band in the ultra-violet region near $26,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. No d-d transition was observed, perhaps obscured by extended tail of charge transfer band. However, the reflectance spectra of these complexes exhibit two weak and broad shoulders near $22,000$ and $18,180\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands are assigned to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ with spin orbit split of ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ state or the second may be due to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$. But this last transition is rarely observed as it involves two electron transitions and the intensity is very small.¹³ The reflectance spectra (Table-A) of the bis chelated complexes also show a shoulder

near 21,800 cm^{-1} and a relatively strong and less broad band near 18,500—20,400 cm^{-1} . The intensity of the second band increases in the order $\text{NCS} < \text{Cl} < \text{Br}$. The occurrence of strong and less broad band in the spectra of bis chelated complexes may be due to increased tetragonality of the ligand field due to mixing of dissimilar weak ligands.

The electronic reflectance and absorption spectra of bis and tris chelated nickel(II) complexes exhibit only two d-d bands (ν_1 and ν_2) in visible and near infrared region. The ϵ_{max} values of these bands are in the range 8—25 and the ratio of ν_2/ν_1 transition lie between 1.8 and 1.6 which are characteristic of octahedral nickel(II) complexes.¹⁷ The tris chelated nickel(II) complex perchlorate $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ exhibits reflectance band at 10,870(ν_1) and 17,850 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and are assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ transitions respectively. The diaquo-bis chelated complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{++}$ and diacido complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2]$ (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- and NCS^-) exhibit these d-d transitions at slightly lower energies (Table—A) than the tris chelate. In methanol or DMF solutions the band positions of the complexes do not shift appreciably, showing that the same species exist in solid as well as in solutions. Besides these d-d transitions the complexes also exhibit an intense charge transfer band near 25,000 cm^{-1} which probably obscures the third band $\nu_3 = {}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ expected for octahedral Ni(II) complexes. From ν_1 and ν_2 band the qualitative value of the energy of the third transition (ν_3) has been obtained with the help of Tanabe and Sugano energy level diagram.¹⁸ Either in strong or weak field approach, the energy of the two components of ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ arising from ${}^3\text{F}$ and ${}^3\text{P}$ states are given by¹⁹ $=(7.5B') + 0.3(\Delta) \pm \frac{1}{2}[(15B')^2 - 18B'\Delta + \Delta^2]^{1/2}$. Following the above expression, the energy of ν_1 and ν_2 transitions have been calculated (Table—D) and found to be approximately equal to the experimental results. The value of Nephelauxetic coefficient β , spin orbit coupling constant λ and the Lande 'g' factor of $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ have been calculated²⁰ and found to be $\beta = 0.93$, $\lambda = 194 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $g = 2.14$. It is expected that bis chelated complexes of type $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{++}$ should have D_{4h} symmetry. However, the electronic reflectance spectra of these complexes do not show the presence of shoulder or any pronounced asymmetry, indicating that tetragonal distortion in these complexes are fairly small.

The value of $10Dq$ of PBH in tris chelated complex perchlorate, $[\text{Ni}(\text{PBH})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \rightarrow (10870 \text{ cm}^{-1})$ is greater than those of ammonia $\{[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}\}$ —

10,500 cm^{-1} } but smaller than ethylenediamine complex $\{[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}\}$ —11,500 cm^{-1} ²¹. Thus the ligand lies between ammonia and ethylenediamine in spectrochemical series.

TABLE C—COLOUR, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE VALUE IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION (28°C) OF SOME Co(III), Rh(III) AND Ir(III) COMPLEXES WITH 2-(2'-PYRIDYL) BENZIMIDAZOLE

Compounds	Colour	Molar conductance value λ_m ohm $^{-1}$ cm 2
$[\text{CoL}_3]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange-yellow	374
$[\text{CoL}_3]\text{Br}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	„	350
$[\text{CoL}_3](\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	„	368
$[\text{Co}(\text{PB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{I}$	„	98
$[\text{Co}(\text{PB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	„	108
$[\text{Co}(\text{PB})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	„	113
$[\text{RhL}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dull-yellow	112
$[\text{RhL}_2\text{I}_2]\text{I}$	Red	—
$[\text{IrL}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange-yellow	98
$[\text{IrL}_2\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$	Orange	—
$[\text{IrL}_2\text{I}_2]\text{I}$	Brown	—
$[\text{IrL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_2$	Pale-yellow	—

Copper(II) complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2]$ exhibit a broad asymmetric band around 12,500—16,600 cm^{-1} and are given in Table—B. The reflectance band positions of the bis chelated complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2$ (where $\text{X} = \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-$, $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$, Cl^- and Br^-) slightly changes from one compound to another and the positions of the band maxima are in the order, $\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} \approx \text{Cl}^- \approx \text{Br}^-$, which suggests that energy level of copper(II) ions are effected by different anions. The diacido complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBH})_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- and NCS^-) also exhibit a broad and asymmetric band and the energy of band maxima are in the order $\text{NCS}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^-$. The broad and asymmetric band of copper(II) complexes at lower energy than planar and octahedral copper(II) complexes are suggestive of their tetragonally distorted octahedral structure.

The electronic spectra of Co(III), Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Ir(III) complexes are of not much help

TABLE D—CRYSTAL FIELD PARAMETERS OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES.

Compounds	Medium	ν_1 cm ⁻¹	${}^3A_{2g}$ 1E_g cm ⁻¹	ν_2 cm ⁻¹		ν_3 cm ⁻¹		Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	β'
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.			
[Ni(NH ₃) ₆]Cl ₂	NH ₄ OH	10,526	13,412	17,241	16,996	28,011	28,232	1050	911	0.87
[Ni(en) ₃]SO ₄	Water	11,500	12,400	18,650	18,670	30,000	30,350	1150	940	0.90
[Ni(PBH) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂	Solid	10,870	—	17,870	17,665	29,340	29,492	1087	890	0.93
Ni(PB) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Solid	10,860	—	17,670	17,562	29,440	29,552	1086	969	0.93
[Ni(PBH) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Solid	10,416	13,160	16,950	16,850	28,470	28,345	1041	946	0.91
[Ni(PBH) ₂ Cl ₂]	Solid	10,180	—	16,210	16,519	27,705	27,815	1018	925	0.89
[Ni(PBH) ₂ Br ₂]	Solid	10,100	—	16,621	16,455	27,450	27,615	1010	918	0.88
[Ni(PBH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Solid	10,416	—	16,830	16,602	27,624	27,868	1041	926	0.89

in the investigation of configuration since these only exhibit strong charge transfer bands in which the expected d-d transitions of the metal complexes are obscured.

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